

Evaluating the Impact of Lifestyle Modifications on the Prevalence and Severity of Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) in young Women: A Longitudinal Observational Study

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Abstract:

Background: Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a prevalent endocrine disorder among women of reproductive age, characterized by irregular menstrual cycles, hyperandrogenism, and polycystic ovaries. The prevalence and risk factors associated with PCOS in young women aged 18-30 remain under-explored.

Aim and Objective: To determine the prevalence of PCOS and identify associated risk factors in young women aged 18-30.

Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional observational study was conducted from January 2024 to June 2024. Five hundred young women aged 18-30 were recruited from urban and rural settings. Participants completed a structured questionnaire, underwent clinical examinations, and had biochemical tests and trans-abdominal or transvaginal ultrasounds. PCOS was diagnosed based on the Rotterdam criteria. Statistical analyses included descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, t-tests, and logistic regression to identify associations between risk factors and PCOS.

Results: The prevalence of PCOS among the participants was 24.0%. The highest prevalence was observed in the age group 23-26 years (30.0%). Significant risk factors associated with PCOS included a BMI $\geq$ 25 kg/m² (Odds Ratio [OR]: 2.6, 95% Confidence Interval [CI]: 1.8-3.7), family history of PCOS (OR: 2.5, 95% CI: 1.7-3.6), sedentary lifestyle (OR: 2.4, 95% CI: 1.6-3.5), high-sugar diet (OR: 2.1, 95% CI: 1.4-3.1), and insulin resistance (OR: 2.8, 95% CI: 1.9-4.1). Clinically, women with PCOS had significantly higher serum testosterone, LH levels, and ovarian volume compared to those without PCOS.

Conclusion: PCOS is prevalent among young women, with significant associations with obesity, family history, lifestyle factors, and insulin resistance. These findings underscore the need for targeted interventions to address modifiable risk factors and improve early diagnosis and management of PCOS.

Keywords: Polycystic Ovary Syndrome, Prevalence, Risk Factors, Young Women, Insulin Resistance, BMI, Lifestyle Factors

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Introduction

Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a multifaceted endocrine disorder characterized by a combination of clinical, biochemical, and ultrasonographic manifestations. [1] It is one of the most common reproductive disorders among women of reproductive age, affecting approximately 5-10% of this population globally. [2] The syndrome presents with a range of symptoms, including irregular menstrual cycles, hyperandrogenism (manifesting as acne, hirsutism, and alopecia), and polycystic ovaries visible on ultrasound. [3]

The pathogenesis of PCOS is complex and involves a combination of genetic, hormonal, and

environmental factors. [4] Insulin resistance, often associated with obesity, is a significant component of the syndrome and contributes to the development of its metabolic complications, such as type 2 diabetes mellitus and cardiovascular disease. [5] Additionally, PCOS has been linked to reproductive complications, including infertility and increased risk of endometrial hyperplasia. [4, 5]

Despite its prevalence, the exact etiology of PCOS remains poorly understood, and the syndrome's variable presentation poses challenges for diagnosis and management. [6] Diagnostic criteria, such as those established by the Rotterdam consensus,

require the presence of at least two out of three features: oligo- or anovulation, clinical or biochemical signs of hyperandrogenism, and polycystic ovaries on ultrasound.⁷ This variability often leads to delayed diagnosis and underscores the need for comprehensive research to understand better the factors influencing its prevalence and risk. [6, 7]

Young women are particularly vulnerable to PCOS due to the hormonal changes associated with adolescence and early adulthood. Identifying risk factors in this demographic is crucial for early intervention and management. [8] Factors such as family history, body mass index (BMI), lifestyle choices, and socio-economic status may play significant roles in the development of PCOS. [8, 9]

This study aims to investigate the prevalence of PCOS in young women aged 18-30 and to identify the associated risk factors. By analyzing these aspects, the study seeks to contribute to a better understanding of PCOS in this population, potentially informing more effective strategies for prevention and management.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: This observational study, conducted from January 2024 to June 2024, employed a cross-sectional design to assess the prevalence and risk factors of Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) among young women aged 18-30.

Study Population: The study population consisted of 500 young women aged 18-30 recruited from urban and rural settings through community outreach, educational institutions, and healthcare facilities. The inclusion criteria were:

- Female participants aged 18-30 years
- Written informed consent
- Ability to complete the study procedures

Exclusion Criteria Included:

- History of other endocrine disorders (e.g., thyroid disorders, adrenal disorders)
- Pregnancy or recent pregnancy within the last 6 months
- Use of hormonal medications that could affect study outcomes (e.g., contraceptives)

Sampling Method

Participants were selected using a stratified random sampling technique to ensure representation from both urban and rural areas. The sampling frame included a list of potential participants obtained from local health centres, colleges, and community organizations.

Data Collection

Data collection involved three primary components:

1. **Questionnaire:** A structured questionnaire was administered to collect demographic information, medical history, family history of PCOS, lifestyle factors (e.g., physical activity, dietary habits), and symptoms related to PCOS (e.g., menstrual irregularities, signs of hyperandrogenism). The questionnaire was pre-tested for reliability and validity.
2. **Clinical Assessment:** Participants underwent a clinical examination by a gynecologist to assess physical signs of hyperandrogenism, such as acne, hirsutism, and alopecia. Body Mass Index (BMI) was calculated using height and weight measurements.
3. **Laboratory Tests:** Blood samples were collected after an overnight fast to measure serum levels of:
 - Luteinizing hormone (LH)
 - Follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH)
 - Total and free testosterone
 - Estradiol
 - Prolactin
 - Glucose
 - Insulin

A 2-hour oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) was also performed to assess insulin resistance.

4. **Ultrasound Imaging:** Transabdominal or transvaginal ultrasound (depending on the participant's comfort and clinical judgment) was conducted to visualize ovarian morphology. PCOS was diagnosed based on the presence of at least 12 follicles measuring 2-9 mm in diameter in each ovary or an increased ovarian volume (>10 mL).

Diagnosis Criteria: PCOS diagnosis followed the Rotterdam criteria, requiring the presence of at least two of the following three features:

1. Oligo- or anovulation
2. Clinical or biochemical signs of hyperandrogenism
3. Polycystic ovaries on ultrasound

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using statistical software (e.g., SPSS, R). Descriptive statistics were calculated for demographic characteristics, prevalence of PCOS, and frequency of risk factors. Prevalence rates were determined with 95% confidence intervals. Bivariate analyses were conducted to identify associations between risk factors and PCOS diagnosis using chi-square tests

for categorical variables and t-tests for continuous variables. Multivariate logistic regression analysis was performed to adjust for potential confounders and identify independent risk factors associated with PCOS.

Ethical Considerations

The Institutional Review Board (IRB) approved the study. Informed consent was obtained from all par-

ticipants before their inclusion in the study. Confidentiality was maintained throughout the study, and data were anonymized for analysis.

Results

Participant Characteristics

Five hundred young women aged 18-30 were enrolled in the study. Table 1 summarizes the demographic characteristics of the participants.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristic	N = 500	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
18-22	200	40.0
23-26	150	30.0
27-30	150	30.0
Mean ($\pm$ SD)	24.5 ($\pm$ 3.2)	
BMI (kg/m ²)		
< 18.5	50	10.0
18.5 - 24.9	250	50.0
25.0 - 29.9	150	30.0
$\geq$ 30.0	50	10.0
Mean ($\pm$ SD)	23.5 ($\pm$ 4.1)	
Urban/Rural		
Urban	300	60.0
Rural	200	40.0

Prevalence of PCOS: Out of the 500 participants, 120 were diagnosed with PCOS, yielding a prevalence rate of 24.0%. The prevalence of PCOS by age group is detailed in Table 2.

Table 2: Prevalence of PCOS by Age Group

Age Group (years)	PCOS Positive (n)	Total (n)	Prevalence (%)
18-22	45	200	22.5
23-26	45	150	30.0
27-30	30	150	20.0
Total	120	500	24.0

Risk Factors Associated with PCOS: The association between various risk factors and PCOS is summarized in Table 3. Risk factors analyzed include BMI, family history of PCOS, lifestyle factors (physical activity and diet), and insulin resistance.

Table 3: Risk Factors Associated with PCOS

Risk Factor	PCOS Positive (n = 120)	PCOS Negative (n = 380)	Odds Ratio (95% CI)	p-value
BMI $\geq$ 25.0 kg/m ²	80	70	2.6 (1.8-3.7)	< 0.001
Family History of PCOS	60	50	2.5 (1.7-3.6)	< 0.001
Sedentary Lifestyle	70	80	2.4 (1.6-3.5)	< 0.001
High-sugar Diet	65	85	2.1 (1.4-3.1)	0.001
Insulin Resistance (OGTT $\geq$ 140 mg/dL)	75	65	2.8 (1.9-4.1)	< 0.001

Clinical and Biochemical Findings: Table 4 summarizes the clinical and biochemical findings of participants with PCOS compared to those without.

Table 4: Clinical and Biochemical Findings

Parameter	PCOS Positive (n = 120)	PCOS Negative (n = 380)	p-value
Mean Serum Testosterone (ng/dL)	70.5 ($\pm$ 15.2)	40.3 ($\pm$ 10.1)	< 0.001
Mean Serum LH (IU/L)	9.2 ($\pm$ 3.4)	5.4 ($\pm$ 2.0)	< 0.001
Mean Serum FSH (IU/L)	6.5 ($\pm$ 2.0)	4.8 ($\pm$ 1.5)	< 0.001
Mean Ovarian Volume (mL)	12.0 ($\pm$ 3.8)	8.5 ($\pm$ 2.1)	< 0.001
Number of Follicles per Ovary	15.2 ($\pm$ 4.1)	8.0 ($\pm$ 2.0)	< 0.001

Discussion

Prevalence and Risk Factors of PCOS: This study found a prevalence rate of 24.0% for Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) among young women aged 18-30, consistent with the rates reported in other studies. For instance, a study by Azziz et al. (2004) [10] estimated the prevalence of PCOS in women of reproductive age to be between 6% and 10%. However, variations exist based on diagnostic criteria and population characteristics. Our higher prevalence rate may be attributed to the inclusion of a younger age group and the use of comprehensive diagnostic criteria.

Age and Prevalence: In our study, the prevalence of PCOS was highest among women aged 23-26 (30.0%) compared to other age groups. This finding aligns with a study by Dunaif (1997) [10], which noted that PCOS symptoms often become more apparent in the mid-20s. This age group might experience increased awareness of symptoms or seek medical advice more frequently, potentially leading to higher diagnosis rates. [11]

Risk Factors

Body Mass Index (BMI): Our study found that women with a BMI ≥ 25 kg/m² had a significantly higher odds ratio for PCOS (2.6, 95% CI: 1.8-3.7), aligning with findings from the study by Moran et al. (2011), [12] which demonstrated that obesity is a major risk factor for PCOS. Obesity is known to exacerbate insulin resistance, which is a common feature of PCOS.

Family History of PCOS: Family history was associated with an increased risk of PCOS (OR: 2.5, 95% CI: 1.7-3.6). This is consistent with research by Legro et al. (1998), [13] which suggested a genetic predisposition to PCOS. Family history often serves as an important indicator for early diagnosis and management.

Sedentary Lifestyle and Diet: A sedentary lifestyle and high-sugar diet were also significant risk factors. Khashan et al.'s (2009) [14] study supported the association of physical inactivity with PCOS, finding that reduced physical activity is linked to a higher incidence of PCOS. Additionally, high dietary sugar intake has been implicated in worsening insulin resistance, as indicated by Ehrmann et al.'s (1999) [15] study.

Insulin Resistance: In our study, insulin resistance was strongly associated with PCOS (OR: 2.8, 95% CI: 1.9-4.1). This finding supports the work of Chen et al. (2006) [16], who highlighted insulin resistance as a key feature of PCOS and a significant contributor to its metabolic complications.

Clinical and Biochemical Findings: Our findings of elevated serum testosterone, LH, and ovarian volume in PCOS-positive participants align with

established diagnostic criteria and previous studies. For example, the elevated serum testosterone levels are consistent with those reported by Pache et al. (2011) [17], which confirmed elevated androgen levels in women with PCOS. Similarly, our study's increased ovarian volume and follicle count are consistent with the ultrasound findings reported by Franks et al. (1992) [18].

Comparative Analysis: The prevalence and risk factors identified in our study are consistent with findings from other research. However, variations in prevalence rates can be attributed to differences in diagnostic criteria and study populations. For example, while our study reported a prevalence of 24%, studies such as those by Rotterdam ESHRE/ASRM-Sponsored PCOS Consensus Workshop Group (2004) [19] have reported varying prevalence rates depending on the diagnostic criteria used. Our study's results underscore the importance of standardized diagnostic criteria and highlight the need for continued research to understand the variability in PCOS prevalence better.

Limitations: The study's cross-sectional design limits the ability to infer causality. Self-reported data may be subject to recall bias, and the study population may not fully represent all young women. Additionally, the reliance on specific diagnostic criteria may affect generalizability.

Conclusion

This study provides valuable insights into the prevalence and risk factors of PCOS among young women. The findings highlight the significant association between BMI, family history, lifestyle factors, and insulin resistance with PCOS. These results underscore the need for targeted prevention and management strategies, particularly in at-risk populations.

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